

A New Synthesis of Afromosin

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Afromosin occurring in *Afromosia elata* has now been synthesised from 6,7,4'-trihydroxyisoflavone by stages of 7-benylation, methylation, and debenylation; it does not undergo nuclear methylation.

Afromosin, isolated recently by McMurry and Theng (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1491) from the hardwood of *Afromosia elata* Harms, has been shown to be 6, 4'-dimethoxy-7-hydroxyisoflavone (X) by a detailed study of its derivatives and degradation products. The structure has further been confirmed by its synthesis as follows. It started from a difficultly accessible 4-methoxyresorcinol, which after condensation with *p*-methoxybenzyl cyanide yielded 2, 4-dihydroxy-5-methoxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl ketone. This deoxybenzoin was subjected to Farkas' method of isoflavone synthesis using zinc cyanide when afromosin could be isolated in nearly 20% yield.

An important feature of this compound is that it is a partial methyl ether with the 7-hydroxyl free. In isoflavones, this hydroxyl is known to be the most reactive (Narasimhachari and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1950, 32A, 342) and this explains why many of the partial methyl ethers are 7-methoxy compounds. When this 7-hydroxyl is free, it should arise from earlier protection by some means, e.g., glycoside formation and subsequent methylation of other hydroxyl groups. In laboratory syntheses, instead of glycoside formation, benzylation has been conveniently used in a number of cases. A similar procedure has now been adopted for the convenient synthesis of afromosin.

The first stage is the preparation of 6,7,4'-trimethoxyisoflavone (VI), which is conveniently made from the deoxybenzoin (III) by condensation with ethyl formate in presence of sodium. The initial product of this reaction is a 2-hydroxyisoflavanone (V), which with acetic anhydride undergoes dehydration to provide the required isoflavone. The deoxybenzoin (III) itself was obtained in two ways. The first and better method consists of the Friedel-Crafts reaction using 1, 2, 4-trimethoxybenzene (IV) (Müller *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 472) and *p*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride (Kindler, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1927, 265, 389), and the second method involves alkaline persulphate oxidation of the easily made phenylbenzyl ketone (I) (Badcock *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2961) and subsequent partial methylation. It agrees in its properties with the sample prepared by McMurry and Theng (*loc. cit.*) by the Hoesch reaction using 3, 4-dimethoxyphenol and 4-methoxybenzyl cyanide.

Demethylation of 6, 7, 4'-trimethoxyisoflavone (VI) could best be effected with anhydrous aluminium chloride and benzene; McMurry and Theng (*loc. cit.*) used hydriodic acid and phenol. The later steps in the synthesis of afromosin are partial benzylation in 7-position, methylation, and debenylation (VIII-X). The synthetic product has all the properties reported for the natural afromosin.

McMurry and Theng reported that when afromosin was methylated using methyl iodide, potassium carbonate, and acetone, they obtained a product different from *O*-methylafromosin (VI) and considered it to be a *C*-methyl derivative. Except in the case of carbonyl derivatives of phloroglucinol, this method does not effect *C*-methylation, and particularly no case is known so far in the flavonoid series. Further, afromosin does not have the necessary structure for *C*-methylation (Jain and Seshadri, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14A, 227; *Quart. Rev.*, 1956, 10, 169). Hence we have examined this point and found that afromosin forms only the *O*-methyl derivative (VI). As a parallel case, 6, 7-dihydroxyisoflavone has also been examined and found to yield only the *O*-methyl derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ultraviolet absorption data were taken in methanol solution (unless otherwise stated).

2, 5-Dihydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (II).—2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl 4-methoxybenzyl ketone (I) was prepared by methylation of 2, 4-dihydroxyphenyl 4-methoxybenzyl ketone using dimethyl sulphate (1.1 *M*) (Badcock *et al.*, *loc. cit.*, used methyl iodide) and then

used for oxidation as follows. To an ice-cooled and well-stirred solution of the deoxybenzoin (2.72 g.) in aqueous KOH (2.8 g./50 c.c.) and pyridine (10 c.c.) was added potassium persulphate (3 g.) in water (30 c.c.) dropwise during 2 hours. After stirring for another 2 hours in an ice bath and subsequently leaving it overnight at room temperature, it was acidified to Congo red and extracted with ether to remove the unchanged product. The aqueous layer was heated with HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) and sodium sulphite for 30 minutes, cooled, and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution furnished a solid (0.6 g.), which crystallised from ether-petroleum ether as pale yellow plates tapering at the ends; m.p. 133-34°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 240, 280, and 353 m μ (log ϵ , 4.16, 4.11, and 3.94 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$ 237, 258, and 315 m μ (log ϵ , 4.15, 3.65, and 3.39 respectively). (Found: C, 65.7; H, 5.5. C₁₆H₁₆O₅ requires C, 66.6; H, 5.6%). It develops a green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-4, 5-dimethoxyphenyl-4-methoxybenzyl Ketone (III).—(a). The above ketone (II) (1.44 g.), dimethyl sulphate (0.5 c.c.), and dry potassium carbonate (2.5 g.) were refluxed in acetone medium for 4 hours. Acetone was distilled off and the residue treated with water (50 c.c.). The insoluble solid crystallised from ethanol as colorless plates (1.2 g.), m.p. 99-100°; bluish green ferric reaction; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 280 and 345 m μ (log ϵ , 4.15 and 3.97 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 255 and 305 m μ (log ϵ , 3.65 and 3.49 respectively). (Found: C, 67.1; H, 6.5. C₁₇H₁₈O₅ requires C, 67.5; H, 6.0%).

(b). An ethereal solution of 1, 2, 4-trimethoxybenzene (IV) (8.5 g./50 c.c.) was added in one lot to an ice-cold ethereal solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (27.2 g./400 c.c.) and it was followed by dropwise addition of *p*-methoxyphenylacetyl chloride (9.5 g.) during 2 hours. After leaving for 24 hours at room temperature, ether was distilled and the residual deep green complex decomposed by keeping it in contact with ice (200 g.) and HCl (conc., 135 c.c.) for 2 hours. The clear liquid was decanted and the semi-solid mass was macerated with a small amount of ether, when a colorless solid separated. It crystallised from ether-petroleum ether as colorless plates, m.p. 99-100°, alone or when mixed with the above sample.

6, 7, 4'-Trimethoxyisoflavone (VI).—A solution of the above deoxybenzoin (III) (4.5 g.) in freshly distilled ethyl formate (350 c.c.) was added slowly to pulverised sodium (3.7 g.) while the resulting mixture was cooled in ice, and shaken. After leaving for 48 hours at room temperature, ice was added to decompose the unchanged sodium, and the whole mixture was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with 2% aqueous NaOH, followed by water, dried, and concentrated when a colorless solid (2.5 g.) was left behind. It crystallised from ethanol as colorless, tiny prisms and melted at 142°, resolidified and remelted at 172-73°, and seemed to consist of 6, 7, 4'-trimethoxy-2-hydroxyisoflavanone (V). [Found (air-dried): C, 63.7; H, 6.3. C₁₈H₁₈O₆, $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires C, 63.7; H, 5.6%).

The above solid was refluxed with acetic anhydride for 1 hour, cooled and poured into ice. The colorless solid, thus obtained, crystallised from ethanol as colorless plates, m.p. 174-75°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 and 318 m μ (log ϵ , 4.60 and 4.19 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$ 235 and 297 m μ (log ϵ , 4.41 and 4.03 respectively). It showed no ferric reaction. McMurry and Theng (*loc. cit.*) also report the same properties.

6,7,4'-Trihydroxyisoflavone (VII).—The above isoflavone (VI) (2 g.), dry aluminium chloride (10 g.) and benzene (240 c.c.) were refluxed for 10 hours; benzene was distilled under vacuum and the residue treated with ice (50 g.) and HCl (conc., 50 c.c.). After leaving the mixture overnight, a colorless solid (0.7 g.) was obtained. It crystallised from methanol as colorless needles, m.p. 320-22° (decomp.) (lit., m.p. 322°, decomp.); $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 and 325 m μ (log ϵ , 4.45 and 4.48).

respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$ 335 and 298 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.29 and 3.91 respectively). It gave a green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

6,4'-Dihydroxy-7-benzoyloxyisoflavone (VIII).—An acetone solution of the above isoflavone (0.7 g.) was refluxed with benzyl chloride (0.3 c.c.), dry sodium iodide (1.5 g.), and ignited potassium carbonate for 5 hours. The inorganic salts were filtered, the acetone solution was concentrated to 10 c.c., and diluted with water (20 c.c.). After leaving it overnight, a colorless solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether (60–80°) when the 7-benzyl ether of the isoflavone (0.45 g.) was obtained as colorless, narrow, rectangular plates, m.p. 231–33°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 262 and 328 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.47 and 4.06 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$, 237 and 300 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.27 and 3.88 respectively). (Found: C, 73.1; H, 5.3. $C_{22}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 73.3; H, 4.4%). It gave a negative ferric reaction.

6,4'-Dimethoxy-7-benzoyloxyisoflavone (IX).—The above benzoyloxyisoflavone (VIII) (360 mg.) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.22 c.c.) and freshly ignited potassium carbonate (1 g.) in dry acetone solution (50 c.c.) for 12 hours. After removal of acetone, water was added to the residue when a colorless solid (350 mg.) was obtained. It crystallised from ethyl acetate as colorless, rectangular plates and needles, m.p. 150–51°; $\lambda_{\max}$ 260 and 318 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.37 and 3.95 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}$ 237 and 297 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.16 and 3.75 respectively). (Found: C, 74.5; H, 5.6. $C_{24}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 74.2; H, 5.2%).

Afrososin (6, 4'-*Dimethoxy-7-hydroxyisoflavone*) (X).—The above isoflavone (IX) (150 mg.), acetic acid (8.5 c.c.), and HCl (conc., 5 c.c.) were heated on a boiling water bath for 2 hours. Acetic acid was partially distilled off under vacuum and the residue treated with water. A white solid separating was collected and it crystallised from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 228–29°; yield 75 mg., $\lambda_{\max}^{EtOH}$ 255 and 325 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.41 and 4.04 respectively); $\lambda_{\min}^{EtOH}$ 237 and 295 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.28 and 3.88 respectively). IR in KBr: 3.18 (O—H), 6.20 (pyrone C=O), 6.43 and 6.68 (aromatic C=C), 7.9 (aromatic C—O), and 9.62 μ (O—Me). In all these properties it agrees with the description of McMurry and Theng (*loc. cit.*) for the natural sample.

Methylation of Afrososin (X) with Methyl Iodide.—Afrososin (X) (100 mg.) was refluxed with methyl iodide (2 c.c.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in dry acetone (20 c.c.) for 12 hours. The product was worked up as usual and it crystallised from ethanol as colorless plates (95 mg.), m.p. 174–75° alone or when mixed with a synthetic sample of 7-*O*-methylafrososin (VI), reported earlier. The UV spectrum also agreed.

Methylation of 6,7-Dihydroxyisoflavone with Methyl Iodide.—6,7-Dimethoxyisoflavone was prepared by the method of Ballio and Pocchiari (*Gazzetta*, 1949, 79, 913) and demethylated with aluminium chloride and benzene. The 6,7-dihydroxyisoflavone (0.180 g.) obtained was methylated with methyl iodide as described in the case of afrososin, when the product (0.150 g.) was found to be identical with 6,7-dimethoxyisoflavone, m.p. 170–71°.